

**THE MODERN TREND OF LIBERALIZING VIEWS ON
IDEOLOGICAL THREATS AND THE EXPERIENCE OF THE UNITED
STATES**

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One of the greatest achievements of human civilization in political science is undoubtedly liberalism. [1] Of the capitalism, communism, imperialism and other political systems that ruled in the 19th and 20th centuries, only liberalism gives a person freedom of thought and speech, freedom of religion and conscience, the opportunity to choose the ways of communication and discussion when dealing with other ideologies, made it possible not to be afraid to enter into marriage and social relations with a person belonging to other political or religious views. [2] At present, the idea of liberalizing views on ideological threats has risen to the level of a trend. But this new trend of liberalism has not yet gained its supporters and a solid foundation in world politics.

It has already become a stereotype that the basis of liberalism policy is built on the idea of freedom, equal opportunities and creation of conditions. [3] This should not be the reason for the emergence of misconceptions that the direction of liberalism is to liberalize views on ideological threats, to ensure the free entry of nay odd ideologies into the society, and to create conditions for their activity.

So, how to understand this new trend of liberalism, how to deal with it and what to expect from it?

Liberalization of views on ideological threats is a new direction of libelism, which is becoming a trend, and at the time conflicts of cultures, beliefs, ideas, and interests are resolved by the use of force or by restricting and stopping diplomatic and economic relations at various levels, this new political direction presents the principles of

avoiding such conflicts through taking into account the interests of both sides in solving economic and political issues, and avoiding tension as much as possible in the current period.

Liberalization of views on ideological threats is to refrain from creating an image of an enemy from values that are difficult to match the political and cultural views of the society and citizens with the usual social or cultural life. [4] Controlling a society by threatening through foreign ideologies, increasing the hatred of the society towards them, thus keeping the society under its influence is a sign of anarchist or populist management, and this form of management is completely opposite to liberalization.

Liberalization of views on ideological threats begins with minimizing the risk of communicating with foreign values that are stranger to the cultural life, legislation, and way of life of society. Here successful establishment of communication with foreign ideologies can help to avoid of stereotype and serves to clarify the main goal of stranger ideologies. The next step is to reach an unique consensus and cooperation between people, groups or countries by identifying common interests and harmonies of views. The primary goal of liberalizing views on ideological threats is to understand that the current practice of protecting one's interests through use of force should be replaced by dialogue and the practice of avoiding conflict of interests, by understanding that fighting or having conflicts with stranger culture, ideology, ideas is losing time and material resources. Because in any society, supporters of any idea can be found. This proves that the conflicts between the ideologies are inevitable and a normal process.

Supporters of the policy of liberalizing views on ideological threats are required to: avoid conflicts between cultures, come to mutual agreement with them, end the images of external enemies, develop programs with a humanitarian basis at the state level, to refrain from separatism mood, [5] not to be cold-hearted in the implementation of government decisions for the benefit of the general and future generations, etc. In the case of states based on liberal state system, we can see that on the basis of liberalizing views on ideological threats, the responsibility lies not to provide unlimited

freedom, but to protect one's own freedom and not interfere with the freedom of others.
[6]

What are the practical results of liberal views, liberal political and social system, formation of the people's liberal view of ideological threats?

Let's explore these in the case of the United States of America. The USA, which has the history of the youngest statehood, but currently participates in the summit of the most developed countries of the world as the main coordinator. The American society, which has the largest number of ethnic groups, has experienced internal war twice in its history. How can the representatives of the civilization, which have been at war with each other several times in history due to their culture, ethnicity, religious and ideological views, live in a new country without a sharp conflict of interests?

Political analysts explain this situation by the fact that American statehood and political parties relied on liberalism from the very beginning. [7] It can be said that modern liberalism is modeled on liberalism developed by America for its development. The American view of liberalism defined absolute freedom and equality of citizens as the main point of support, social justice and mixed economy as auxiliary points of support. The fact that US citizens belong to different ethnic groups is theoretically seen as the main factor in the tension between these groups. But as a solution to this in the state, liberalism (free space of ideas and views) and liberal requirements (inviolability of other people's rights, opinions and culture, taking into account the interests of all groups) became the key to solving the problems. According to the rules established in the state, citizens have the right and responsibility to determine the legislation at the state level. [8] In the minds of the citizens, the adopted law formed the world view that the majority of the population of the state have a complex of views and that these views are protected by force. The establishment of the system in this form does not create the need to solve any cultural, social, ideological problem at the state level based on the constitution of the USA and the structure of the state government.

The fact that US legislation is based on a liberal approach to ideological threats in the management of the state and society gave it the following positive results:

- building a state based on racial, national, religious diversity, with the rule of law;
- a controlling system that resolves internal conflicts, disagreements, conflicts of interests at the regional level and does not require consideration at the state level;
- the image of the state where human dignity, personal freedom and inviolability are ensured at the highest level;
- civil society capable of influencing the foreign and domestic policy of the state;
- civil and political consciousness at a level capable of demanding an exit from useless wars in the state's foreign policy.

In addition to these, America has the image of a state that can give everyone the opportunity to live a comfortable life, where legal and social justice flourishes. It is seen as a country of dreams where all the doors of opportunities are open especially for young people who have intellectual potential and are dissatisfied with bureaucratism, anarchism, corruption, monopolies, restriction of freedom of speech and have their own political, economic, plans and visions. The main factor that strengthens this situation is the guarantee that citizens in the USA will not be subject to illegal persecution by laws, government and political groups of the USA, regardless of their social origin, ideology, political, religious views, and type of activity. [9]

The countries that promoted the liberalization of views on ideological threats to high places in their political, legal, economic, and social life (USA, Germany, Great Britain, Norway, Sweden, New Zealand, Canada, Switzerland, Australia, France) [10] in the current development trends considers its positions as the result of the policy of regulating risks in the ideology of individuals and groups.

The population, military-technical development, armament, political or religious fanaticism on our planet has reached such a level that it is logically wrong and impossible to reject the views of world politicians, ideologists, human rights defenders, and peace-loving institutes that the liberalization of views on ideological threats is a periodic necessity.

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